

Quantitative Correlation of the Effect of Changing Alkyl Substitution in Solvent, on Solubility for Alcoholic Solutions

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The solubility of benzoic acid has been determined in two series of aliphatic alcohols. The solubility parameter 'solubilizing number' (N) is defined as solvent-to-solute molar ratio in saturated solution. Logarithm of this parameter gives good linear correlation with the function $\log(1/\mu)$, where μ is the solute-solvent reduced molecular weight. The correlation provides additional evidence that logarithm of reactivity parameters (such as rate and equilibrium constants in earlier cases) of solvation-dependent reactions in alcohols give linear correlation with $\log(1/\mu)$.

Reactivity changes due to changes in alkyl substitution in solvent has been quantitatively correlated to solute-solvent reduced molecular weight, in our earlier work, for reactions in alcoholic solvents. Thus logarithm of rate constant ($\log k$) of *t*-butyl chloride solvolysis and logarithm of equilibrium constant ($\log K$) of keto-enol equilibria of ethyl and methyl acetoacetates have been shown to give good straight-line plots against the function $\log(1/\mu)$, where μ is the solute-solvent reduced molecular weight^{1,2} in aliphatic alcohols of α -series and of normal series; the slopes were different for the two series. The substituent effect was attributed to changing alkyl bulk.

The present work is in continuation of the above, looking for a similar effect due to alkyl substitution in solvent on solubility in the same two series of alcohols and, if a steadily changing bulk effect is observed qualitatively, to see whether it will give the same kind of correlation between the logarithm of the experimental parameter of solubility and $\log(1/\mu)$. Benzoic acid was selected as the solute.

Results and Discussion

The final results of the solubility determination are given in Table 1. It is well-known that solubility is determined by the extent of molecular interaction between solute and solvent molecules. The interaction between the (proton donating) solute benzoic acid and the (strongly ion-solvating) solvent alcohols must be one of hydrogen bonding with alcohols in the role of H-bond acceptors. This interaction is similar to the solvation bonds in the *t*-butyl chloride solvolysis and keto-enol equilibria in the same alcohols; it is the main solvation bond leading to the dissolution of the solute. The solvation bond involves the bulky benzoic acid molecule at one end and the alcohol molecule at the other. Therefore, increasing the bulk of the alcohol by increasing alkyl substitution can affect solvation negatively due to steric hindrance. On the other hand, the same alkyl substitution can have a positive, solvation-strengthening effect due to increasing electron release into the solvation bond.

The experimental results show that (i) alkyl substitution

hardly affects solubility in the normal series of alcohols (molar solubility values remaining practically constant or changing very little in both directions) while (ii) the effect on solubility in alcohols of α -series is regular, molar solubility steadily increasing in the order, methanol < ethanol < iso-propanol < *t*-butanol. The former result may be due to varying polar and steric effects. The latter, however, indicates that polar effect of the alkyl groups is more important than their steric effect qualitatively in determining molar solubility in these alcohols. To test the quantitativity of this effect, these molar solubility values were plotted against the polarity parameter, polar substituent constant (σ^*)³ of the corresponding alkyl group in the alcohol. The plot is linear from methanol to iso-propanol, but solubility in *t*-butanol falls short of the required value for linearity. It would seem that the opposing bulk effect had become large enough at *t*-butanol to more than counteract the polar effect. In short, correlation between polar effect of the substituents (measured in terms of solubility) and the corresponding structural parameter (σ^*) is not quantitative.

At this point, another parameter of solute-solvent interaction was considered: solubilizing number (N) which is defined as the ratio of average number of solvent molecules involved in solvation (directly or indirectly) to number of solute molecule, in saturated solution. The values of N for benzoic acid in the alcohols of α -series are listed in Table 1.

TABLE 1—MOLAR SOLUBILITIES AND SOLUBILIZING NUMBERS (N) OF BENZOIC ACID IN ALCOHOLS WITH THE STRUCTURAL PARAMETERS OF THE ALKYL SUBSTITUENTS IN THE ALCOHOLS

Alcohol	Molar solubility	σ^*	N	E_s	μ
Methanol	0.2223	0.00	4.499	0.00	25.37
Ethanol	0.2566	-0.10	3.898	-0.07	33.43
<i>i</i> -Propanol	0.2873	-0.19	3.481	-0.47	40.25
<i>t</i> -Butanol	0.3092	-0.30	3.234	-1.54	46.10

As is to be expected from the order of the molar solubilities and the fact that N is the inverse ratio of the solubility, the values show the reverse orders qualitatively:

TABLE 2—MOLAR SOLUBILITY OF BENZOIC ACID BY REVERSE TITRATION AND THE CORRESPONDING SOLUBILIZING NUMBER

Wt. of benzoic acid; 9.7696 g (0.08 mol)
Temperature : 35°C

Alcohol	Vol. of consumed turated ml	Alcohol for sat. soln. ml	Alcohol consumed moles	Molar solubility	<i>N</i>
	Titre values	Average volume			
Alcohol (α -series) :					
Methanol	14.4	14.5	0.3599	0.2223	5
	14.6				
	14.5				
Ethanol	18.5	18.4	0.3118	0.2566	4
	18.4				
	18.3				
i-Propanol	21.2	21.3	0.2785	0.2873	3
	21.3				
	21.4				
t-Butanol	24.1	24.3	0.2587	0.3092	4
	24.3				
	24.5				
Alcohol (n-series) :					
Ethanol	18.5	18.4	0.3118	0.2566	4
	18.4				
	18.3				
Propanol	21.1	21.1	0.2824	0.2838	4
	21.0				
	21.2				
Butanol	28.8	29.0	0.3163	0.2529	4
	28.9				
	29.1				
Pentanol	29.5	29.7	0.2740	0.2919	3
	29.7				
	29.8				
Hexanol	43.3	43.4	0.3447	0.2301	4
	43.4				
	43.5				
Heptanol	43.5	43.6	0.3147	0.2542	4
	43.6				
	43.7				
Octanol	47.3	47.3	0.2992	0.2674	4
	47.2				
	47.3				
Nonanol	57.4	57.2	0.320	0.2439	4
	57.2				
	57.0				
Decanol	63.2	63.1	0.3305	0.2420	4
	63.1				
	63.0				

N decreasing with increasing alkyl substitution in the alcohol. However, it is also reasonable that the number of solvent molecules involved in solvation of benzoic acid should decrease with increasing alkyl substitution due to the bulk effect of the alkyl groups. On the basis of this

reasoning, correlation between solubilizing number and bulk parameters was tested for their quantitative character.

Following the linear correlations obtained in the earlier cases for bulk effect (referred to in the introduction), logarithm of the reactivity parameter, N ($\log N$) was plotted against $\log (1/\mu)$. The plot gave a good straight-line. It may be noted that the plot being consisted of just four points is due to the theoretical limitation that carbon has only four valencies at which to change alkyl groups in the α -series. The solubilizing number (N) was also plotted against the steric substituent constant (E_s) but the plot was not linear. This was also the case in the earlier reactions of solvolysis and keto-enol equilibria.

To summarize, the results provide additional evidence to the earlier observation² that (i) alkyl substitution in solvent produces a negative effect on reactivity if the reactivity depends on the degree of solvation and (ii) this effect gives quantitative correlation with a function of reduced alkyl molecular weight of solute and solvent.

Experimental

The alcohols and benzoic acid were purified by the usual methods⁴. Solubility could not be determined by the usual methods⁵ (which were meant for aqueous solutions) due to the rapid evaporation of many of the alcohols. The following method was found suitable by trial-and-error method and was adopted.

A convenient amount of the solute and benzoic acid (9.7696 g, 0.08 mol) in the form of fine powder, was taken in a conical flask and alcohol was added such that the volume was about 50% of that required to make saturated solution (the approximate volume for saturated solution having been estimated earlier). The flask was tightly stoppered and thermostatted at 35° for 15 min. Then, keeping the flask still partially immersed in the bath, more alcohol was added dropwise with vigorous shaking by rotary motion until the last speck of the solid just disappeared with the last drop just added. Repeated trials showed that the end-point was quite clear and reproducible. For each alcohol this 'reverse titration' was done in triplicate (Table 2) and the average value taken. Molar solubility and solubilizing number were then calculated.

References

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